

Separable Physics-Informed Neural Networks for Robust Inverse Quantification in Solid Mechanics

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Abstract

Over the last decade, the emergence of full-field measurement techniques, such as digital image correlation (DIC), has revolutionized material testing. These advancements usher in a new era of material testing 2.0, where tests are designed to extract the most comprehensive information from materials. Established inverse quantification techniques, like the Virtual Fields Method (VFM) and the Finite Element Method Updating (FEMU), have been employed to recover material properties from full-field measurements. However, these methods can struggle with complex material behaviors or partial measurements. Recently, Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINNs) have emerged as a promising alternative to traditional inverse quantification methods. They are particularly well-suited for problems where hidden information needs to be reconstructed. Nevertheless, the convergence of PINNs can be slow and computationally expensive, limiting their practicality. A new architecture called Separable Physics-Informed Neural Networks (SPINNs) was recently introduced to address these limitations. In this work, we demonstrate the superiority of SPINNs over PINNs for both forward and inverse problems in solid mechanics through a simple example. Despite remaining computationally expensive, SPINNs can compete with other inverse quantification techniques from the literature. We use simulated DIC measurements corrupted with Gaussian noise to investigate the accuracy and robustness of these methods.

Keywords: Separable Physics-Informed Neural Networks, Inverse Quantification, Solid Mechanics, Digital Image Correlation

1. Introduction

The field of material testing has undergone a significant transformation with the advancement of full-field measurement techniques like Digital Image Correlation (DIC). These techniques open the door to material testing 2.0, where the tests are designed to extract the most information from the material [1]. However, traditional inverse quantification techniques, such as the Virtual Fields Method (VFM) and the Finite Element Method (FEMU), can struggle with complex material behavior or partial measurements.

In recent years, Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINNs) have emerged as a promising alternative for inverse quantification in solid mechanics. Haghigat et al. (2018) were among the first to introduce PINNs in this field, demonstrating their potential for solving both forward and inverse problems. However, in their work and subsequent studies [2, 3], both displacement and stress data were used to recover material properties. In practice, full-field measurements typically only provide displacement data, posing a challenge.

Later attempts to utilize only displacement data often face issues with slow convergence and high computational demands, limiting their practicality for real-world applications [4, 5]. To address these limitations, this paper leverages a recently introduced architecture called SPINN (Separable-Physics-Informed Neural Network). This framework has been shown to achieve significantly faster convergence compared to traditional PINNs.

In this study, we first introduce the PINNs and SPINN frameworks and then demonstrate the superior performance of SPINN over traditional PINNs in solving both forward and inverse problems through a simple example. We also compare SPINN to other inverse quantification techniques from the literature. Our results show that the improved convergence brought by the SPINN architecture makes it

competitive with traditional inverse quantification methods.

2. Methodology

Since their introduction in 2017 [6, 7], Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINNs) have been widely used to solve partial differential equations (PDEs) in various fields. However, since they are based on a stochastic optimization process, convergence issues can limit their practicality for real-world applications. Indeed, poor convergence affects not only the training time but also the trustworthiness of the results. Therefore, significant efforts have been made recently to improve the convergence of PINNs [8–10]. Recent promising improvements include the introduction of a new architecture called SPINN (Separable-Physics-Informed Neural Network).[11] This architecture has been shown to achieve significantly faster convergence than traditional PINNs. This improvement is achieved by lowering the computational cost and making the optimization process easier. This section will briefly introduce the PINNs and SPINN frameworks.

2.1. Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINNs)

Given their popularity and the number of papers published on the subject, PINNs are only briefly introduced here. The reader can refer to the original paper, or literature reviews for more details. [12, 13]

Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINNs) are a class of neural networks trained to approximate the solution of a boundary value problem (BVP) defined by a partial differential equation (PDE) and boundary conditions :

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{F}_\lambda[u](x) &= f(x) \quad \text{in } \Omega, \\ \mathcal{B}_\lambda[u](x) &= g(x) \quad \text{on } \partial\Omega,\end{aligned}\tag{1}$$

where \mathcal{F}_λ is the PDE operator, \mathcal{B}_λ is the boundary operator, u is the solution, f is the source term, g is the boundary condition and Ω is the domain. The solution u is approx-

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imated by a neural network u_θ with weights θ trained to minimize the loss function $\mathcal{L}_{\text{PINNs}}$ defined as:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{PINNs}} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{physics}} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{IC/BC}} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{data}}, \quad (2)$$

where $\mathcal{L}_{\text{physics}}$ enforces the PDE, $\mathcal{L}_{\text{IC/BC}}$ enforces the initial and boundary conditions, and $\mathcal{L}_{\text{data}}$ enforces the compliance to observed data.

The initial and boundary conditions can also be enforced using a masking function that multiplies the output of the neural network [14]. This approach ensures that the approximation always satisfies the boundary conditions. Therefore it is referred to as *hard constraints* in opposition to the *soft constraints* of an additional loss term. Although hard constraints can be challenging to implement depending on the problem's geometry, they typically result in better convergence.

The available data typically corresponds to measurements in the context of physics problems. Such data isn't mandatory, the solution can be sought with only the PDE and the boundary conditions to solve a so-called *forward problem*. On the other hand, when data is available, it can be used to find parameters λ of the PDE, solving an *inverse problem*.

The most challenging aspect of the PINNs framework lies in the training step, i.e. the optimization process of finding the weights θ that minimize the loss function $\mathcal{L}_{\text{PINNs}}$. This step ensures that the approximated solution u_θ satisfies the PDE, boundary conditions, and any available data. The training process can be computationally expensive and may sometimes fail to converge, heavily relying on numerous hyperparameters, including the neural network architecture and the optimization applied algorithm. Improving the convergence of PINNs is crucial for achieving the accuracy and practicality needed for real-world applications. Consequently, recent literature has focused significantly on better understanding and enhancing the convergence of PINNs. Separable-Physics-Informed Neural Networks (SPINNs) are one of the recent promising improvements in this direction.

2.2. Separable Physics-Informed Neural Networks

Separable-Physics-Informed Neural Networks (SPINNs) were recently introduced by Cho et al. (2023) as an alternative to traditional PINNs [11]. This new architecture has been shown to achieve significantly faster convergence and better final accuracy compared to traditional PINNs. The authors also provide a theoretical background on the universal approximation capability of SPINNs. The observed improvements are attributed to its ability to evaluate the PDE at more points at a lower computational cost.

The SPINN architecture, illustrated in Figure 1, is separable in that each component of the input is processed by a separate neural network before being combined through a dot product. Each of these separate networks, called *body-networks*, has an output size of r , which is the rank of the model. The final dot product step of the SPINN architecture can be seen as a low-rank tensor approximation of the solution [11].

This architecture allows computation of the output at

Figure 1. SPINN architecture for a 3D problem

Figure 2. Illustrative example of factorizable-coordinates constraint required for SPINN sampling

N^d points with only N evaluations of each of the d body-networks. Furthermore, by leveraging forward-mode automatic differentiation, this computational cost is further reduced during the calculation of gradients.

It is important to note that this increased number of points comes with two main constraints. The first one is illustrated in Figure 2. As the output points are the Cartesian product of each coordinate component, they must be factorizable [11], meaning that they must lie on a lattice-like structure. It can be limiting for combining this architecture adaptive sampling strategies [15, 16]. The second constraint brought by the cartesian product is the hypercube-like shape of the output points. This can be problematic for problems with complex geometries, as the output points may not be able to represent the domain accurately. As suggested by the authors, possible solutions to this issue include filtering out the points that are outside the domain or using a mapping function to transform the hypercube into the domain. [11].

The authors achieved better accuracy and faster convergence with SPINN compared to traditional PINNs on various examples, with a computational cost reduced by a factor of 60 in wall-clock time [11]. In the following section, we will show that similar results can be obtained in the field of solid mechanics, for both forward and inverse problems.

3. Comparative experiments

All the experiments were conducted using the open-source physics-informed neural network library *DeepXDE* [17] on a Nvidia Quadro P4000 GPU. The SPINN implementation was directly adapted from the original paper [11] open-source code, using the JAX backend of DeepXDE. The code, extra figures, and animations will be made available on GitHub: www.github.com/bonneted/

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3.1. A simple solid mechanics example

Many examples of the use of PINNs in solid mechanics can be found in the literature. One of the first papers by Haghighat et al. (2020) [18] introduced a convenient toy example to assess the performance of PINNs in solid mechanics.

3.1.1. Problem statement

Figure 3. Boundary conditions of the toy example

This example is shown in Figure 3 and consists of a square domain with boundary conditions and volumetric body forces f chosen to have an analytical solution:

$$\begin{aligned}
 f_x &= -\lambda \left(-\pi Q y^3 \cos(\pi x) + 4\pi^2 \sin(\pi y) \cos(2\pi x) \right) \\
 &\quad - \mu \left(-\pi Q y^3 \cos(\pi x) + \pi^2 \sin(\pi y) \cos(2\pi x) \right) \\
 &\quad - 8\pi^2 \mu \sin(\pi y) \cos(2\pi x) \\
 f_y &= \lambda \left(-3Q y^2 \sin(\pi x) + 2\pi^2 \sin(2\pi x) \cos(\pi y) \right) \\
 &\quad + \mu \left(\frac{\pi^2 Q y^4 \sin(\pi x)}{16} - 6Q y^2 \sin(\pi x) \right) \\
 &\quad + 2\pi^2 \mu \sin(2\pi x) \cos(\pi y)
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

The material is assumed to be linear elastic, the governing equations are the following:

$$\begin{cases} \epsilon_{ij} = \frac{1}{2}(u_{i,j} + u_{j,i}) & \text{small-deformation} \\ \sigma_{ij,j} + f_i = 0 & \text{momentum balance} \\ \sigma_{ij} = \lambda \delta_{ij} \epsilon_{kk} + 2\mu & \text{linear elasticity} \end{cases} \tag{4}$$

where Ω is the domain, σ is the stress tensor, f is the body force, C is the stiffness tensor, ϵ is the strain tensor, and u is the displacement field.

The analytical solution for this problem is given by equation 5 and plotted in Figure 4.

$$\begin{cases} u_x = \cos(2\pi x) \times \sin(\pi y) \\ u_y = \sin(\pi x) \times \frac{Q y^4}{4} \end{cases} \tag{5}$$

Figure 4. Analytical solution of the toy example

3.1.2. Implementation details

To address both the displacement field and the stress field, and to enforce the PDE and material law, various approaches can be implemented to model continuum mechanics using the PINN framework. Following a similar method as Haghighat et al. (2018) [18], we chose to output both the displacement field and the stress field from the neural network, incorporating the PDE and material law as loss terms. For further details on possible implementations, readers are referred to this prior work [19].

The PINN model comprises five independent networks for each output, each containing four hidden layers with 50 neurons and hyperbolic tangent (tanh) activation functions. In the SPINN model, the body-networks consist of four hidden layers with 32 neurons and hyperbolic tangent activation functions. Both models are trained using the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 10^{-3} . The batch size is set to 500 training points sampled using the Hammersley sequence for the PINN and 64^2 grid points for the SPINN.

3.1.3. Forward problem results

As an initial comparison, we address the forward problem where the displacement field is determined without any data. The two models are first compared after two minutes of training time, as illustrated in Figure 5. The SPINN model converges significantly faster than the PINN model in terms of relative mean squared error (MSE). The PINN model seems to get stuck in a local minimum, leading to sharp discontinuities in the displacement field approximation. In contrast, the SPINN model converges smoothly to the analytical solution.

From Figure 6, we can observe that the PINN model continues to improve with longer training times. In this example, after one hour of training, the PINN achieves a similar level of accuracy as the SPINN model does in just five minutes. Moreover, the PINN's convergence appears to be step-wise, getting stuck in consecutive local minima. It's worth mentioning that the PINN model's convergence speed could be improved by fine-tuning training parameters, such as employing an adaptive learning rate or the L-BFGS optimizer. However, this is not the purpose here as both models are compared without any tuning.

Building on these initial findings, the next section will demonstrate that SPINN's superior convergence, observed in numerous examples from the original paper [11], also extends to the inverse problem.

Figure 5. Comparison of the PINN and SPINN models after two minutes of training

Figure 6. Relative mean squared error history of the PINN and SPINN models for one hour of training

3.1.4. Inverse problem results

In the inverse problem, our goal is to recover the material properties λ and μ from known displacement data. We simulate the DIC measurements using the analytical solution on a grid of 10×10 points. An additional data term, equal to the mean squared error of the network's approximation on the grid points, is included in the loss function. The material properties are initialized at $\lambda = 2$ and $\mu = 0.3$, and these values are updated during training. The other hyperparameters remain the same as in the forward problem.

We observe that both models converge to the correct material properties, as shown in Figure 7. However, the SPINN model converges significantly faster, taking just 5 minutes compared to over 30 minutes for the PINN model. Additionally, the PINN model initially diverges significantly from the true values before converging. This damping effect can be mitigated by using a smaller learning rate specifically for the material properties. We also note that the PINN model's convergence is better and smoother than in the forward problem, driven by the additional data term.

Even though SPINN already shows a significant convergence improvement over PINN, this first example remains fairly simple. Therefore, we will now further compare the two models in a more challenging scenario by reducing the number of available data points and introducing noise into the data.

3.1.5. Robustness to noise

The number of available data points is reduced to 6×6 and Gaussian noise with a standard deviation of 0.1 is added to the displacement data. Ten runs are performed for each

Figure 7. Material properties recovery for the PINN (top) and SPINN (bottom) models after 57 and 12 minutes of training, respectively

model to have statistically significant results.

Both models successfully converge to the correct material properties, with the SPINN model achieving convergence much faster than the PINN model (Figure 8 and 9). Despite the difference in convergence speed, both models demonstrate similar final accuracy and parameter recovery, as detailed in Table 1.

In summary, our comparative analysis of the PINN and SPINN models in addressing both forward and inverse problems in solid mechanics demonstrates the superior convergence speed and robustness of SPINN. While the PINN model can achieve comparable accuracy with extended training and parameter tuning, SPINN's ability to converge

Figure 8. Relative mean squared error history of both models for the noisy inverse problem (minimum, maximum, and mean values over 10 runs)

Figure 9. Material properties recovery for both models from noisy data (minimum, maximum, and mean values over 10 runs)

Table 1. Comparison of the PINN and SPINN final results for the noisy inverse problem

Model	Relative MSE	λ	μ	Time
True	–	1.000	0.500	–
PINN	1.52% ±1.10%	0.975 ±0.041	0.507 ±0.0127	40 min
SPINN	1.00% ±0.65%	0.990 ±0.028	0.507 ±0.0131	10 min

rapidly and smoothly makes it a promising approach for practical applications, especially in scenarios with noisy data or limited training points. Building on these findings, it is proposed to study the performances of SPINN compared with other well-established inverse quantification techniques in solid mechanics.

3.2. Side-loaded plate

To compare SPINN’s capability in solving inverse problems with other existing methods, a benchmark example from the literature was selected. Martins (2018) [20] introduced the side-loaded plate example to evaluate the performance of various inverse quantification techniques, including:

- Finite Element Method Updating (FEMU)
- Constitutive Equation Gap Method (CEGM)
- Equilibrium Gap Method (EGM)
- Virtual Fields Method (VFM)

3.2.1. Problem statement

The example at hand involves a side-loaded square plate, measuring $3 \times 3 \text{ mm}^2$ with a thickness of 0.1mm. This plate is composed of a linear elastic material, characterized by a Young’s modulus of $E = 210 \text{ GPa}$ and a Poisson’s ratio of $\nu = 0.3$.

A heterogeneous load, denoted as $f(x, y)$, is applied to the right side of the plate. This load acts in the x direction and its magnitude is linearly increasing: $f_x(x, y) = my + b$. Here, the slope m is 10N/mm and the intercept b is 50N.

In the original paper, the reference solution is computed using Finite-Element Method (FEM) by dividing the plate into 9 plane-stress elements, each with 4 nodes, using bilinear elements. The initial configuration of the plate, the

boundary conditions imposed, and the finite element mesh are all illustrated in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Discretized side-loaded plate example

At first, we replicate the reference FEM solution using Fenics, an open-source finite element library [21]. As the mesh used in the original paper is coarse, the approximation has not converged and we were not able to replicate the exact same results. For this reason, we have decided to use a finer mesh, with 100×100 elements, to ensure that the solution has converged. The reference FEM solution is later denoted by U^* and S^* .

A grid of 6×6 points from the FEM solution is used to simulate the DIC measurements. The implementation of the SPINN model is similar to the previous example, with the same hyperparameters. The results are shown in Figure 11.

The final mean squared error and the recovered material properties are reported in Table 2 in comparison with other methods from Martins (2018) [20].

Table 2. Recovered material properties from different methods

	E (GPa)	ν
Reference	210	0.3
FEMU	210.00	0.300
CEGM	210.00	0.2993
EGM	210.97	0.287
VFM	210.00	0.300
SPINN	209.1	0.284

Although the SPINN model successfully recovers material properties, its accuracy appears slightly lower compared to other methods. Furthermore, achieving convergence with SPINN requires significant training time due to slow convergence rates.

However, it’s crucial to note several points. Firstly, both FEMU and CEGM methods are based on the finite element method, ensuring near-perfect recovery of material properties since they use the same approximation for both reference and optimization. Secondly, VFM can recover the exact material properties for linear elastic materials, as it is the case here.

Considering these factors, SPINN performs similarly to EGM, the only other unbiased method in the comparison.

Despite its computational and convergence challenges, SPINN shows promising results, particularly in achieving good accuracy in Young’s modulus after approximately 20

Figure 11. Material properties recovery for the side-loaded plate example using SPINN

minutes of training. Though slower in converging Poisson's ratio, it reaches acceptable accuracy after an hour of training. Furthermore, the simplicity of the benchmark example favors other existing methods. SPINN could be more competitive in tackling problems that are more challenging for traditional approaches, for example in the case of non-linear material behavior or missing data.

Future research may explore various strategies to enhance SPINN's convergence, such as employing specialized guiding functions for parameter recovery [3] or adopting adaptive sampling techniques [10, 15, 16].

4. Conclusion

This study compared SPINN and PINN models in solving forward and inverse problems in solid mechanics. SPINN demonstrated superior convergence speed, even in scenarios with noisy data or limited training points. It effectively recovered material properties from DIC measurements with accuracy comparable to established inverse quantification techniques. However, more complex examples could be more relevant to demonstrate SPINN's full potential compared to traditional methods that perform well in simple cases. Addressing convergence speed remains critical, but ongoing improvement strategies offer optimism for SPINN's future applications in solid mechanics.

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